

ASSESSMENT OF THIRUKKURAL TRANSLATION - A FUNCTIONAL APPROACH

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Abstract:

Translation is an activity of enormous importance in the modern world and it is a subject of interest not only to linguistics, professionals and amateur translators and language teachers, but are to electronic engineers and mathematicians. Since translation has to do with language, the analysis and description of translation – processes must make considerable use of categories setup for the description of languages. It must, in other words, draw upon a theory of language – a general linguistic theory. Translation is an operation performed on languages; processes of substituting a text in one language for a text in another, clearly, then, any theory of translations must draw upon a theory of language, and it defines to extend a general linguistic theory. Therefore, the aim of this paper is to provide a critical assessment of translation and establish the pragmatic equivalence instead of the better communication in the Source Language into Target Language, thirukkural translated by Rev. G. U. Pope, Drew and Kaviyogi Suthanatha Bharathi. Nevertheless, in the field of translation by the translators strategies such as Steiner (1976), Catford (1965), Nida (1974), House (2001), Toury, (1995), Michael Scriven (2007), Crystal and Davy (1969) Koller (1974), Reiss (1968). The above mentioned the scholars theories are presented to provided a better understanding of the assessment knowledge and how the concept of assessment in translations are measured such a theoretical approach in general and functional approach in particular.

Key Words: Linguistics, Language Teachers, Electronic Engineers, Mathematicians, Critical Assessment & Pragmatic Equivalence

1. Introduction:

Translation is defined as a process of finding a target language equivalent for the source language sentence. In some extreme theoretical positions, equivalence in sometimes defined as identity of not only the content but also the form and the process at various levels of the linguistic structure in the translated materials in the target language. Equivalence is the transfer of the content to the target language in a manner that is acceptable to and is considered as the genius of the target language. This equivalence must be achieved in such a way the ambiguity, interference and variation in meaning are all avoided. The translation should aim at seeking the conceptual equivalent, it should define the conceptual equivalents accurately and render them in the linguistic terms of the target language.

Translation, otherwise, can be defined as the replacement of textual material in one language (i.e., the source language (hereafter SL) by equivalent textual material in another language (i.e., the target language (hereafter TL). There are linguistic models that generally approach the translation process as mainly concerned with a special type of relation that exists between languages. It is axiomatic in linguistics that materials of any one language can be translated into any other language. The axiom operates in close conjunction with another characteristic of language, viz., and affability. The linguistic models of translation attempt are the same to identify the structural carriers of content in the SL so as to provide an effective transfer of content in the TL, whenever the possibility of the closest similar structure is more important and without affecting the genius of target language.

Catford (1965: 13) treats the equivalences between languages from the point of view of the levels of the structure the linguists description provide. He employs the Hollidayan model of grammar and builds up a model of linguist's translation. Though linguists may generally agree with the definition of translation given in the beginning, the underlying assumptions, the procedures they follow, for the identification and validation of equivalences, and the levels of structure for which such equivalences are sought, may differ from one school of linguistics to another. Nida (1974: 41) on the other hand, while accepting and positing linguistic levels of equivalences, suggests that shifting is the focus in translating from the form of the message (seeking equivalences in matters such as rhymes, rhythms, parallelisms and unusual grammatical structural) to the response to the receptor. The translator should bear in his mind the audience for whom he is translating. Nida opines that each language has its own genius and that if we want to communicate effectively, we must respect the genius of the language. Each language covers the totality of experience with symbols, and each language has its own system of symbolizing meaning. The translator should aim at reproducing the meaning of a text, so as to be understood by the writer. In short, Nida argues in favour of a dynamic equivalence which is defined in terms of the degree to which the receptors of the message in the receptor language respond to it in substantially the same manner as the receptors in the SL, this responses can never be identical, for the cultural and historical

settings are of two different nature, but there should be a high degree of equivalence of response. Or the translation will have failed to accomplish its purpose. Nida says the above as generally true of translating, but more specifically in the context of translating the bible.

2. Pragmatic Model of Translation:

This model defines translation as the replacement of a text in the SL by a semantically and pragmatically equivalent text in the TL. The model suggests that the essence of translation lies in the preservation of the semantic, pragmatic and textual aspects of meaning. The semantic aspects consist of the relationship of reference or denotation the relationship of linguistic units or symbols to their referents. Pragmatics, on the other hand, is the study of purposes for which sentences are used. It is a study of the real world conditions under which a sentence may be appropriately used as an utterance. Pragmatics, thus relates to the correlation between linguistic units and the users of these units in a given communication situation. The connotative meaning also forms part of pragmatic meaning. The textual aspects of meanings are those features that make a text a cohesive whole; these include occurrence of pro-forms, substitutions, co-references, ellipses and anaphora. The methods of operation of the pragmatic models consist of the following steps: a given source text is analysed according to a set of eight dimensions, three language user dimensions (geographical origin, social class and time) and five language use dimensions (medium, participation, social role relationship, social attitude and province) for which linguistic (syntactic, lexical and textual) correlates are established; and then, attempts are made to have these transferred in the target language. Functional equivalence is the goal of this model.

3. Traditional Model of Translation:

This model interprets the operation of translating as consisting in the transfer of some neutral extralingual meaning from one linguistic expression to another. But one should make sure of the thing that content exists independent of language, and sees to it how one can transfer the independent content from one language to another.

4. Translation as Parody or Versions:

This model suggests that there is some similarity of purpose between parody and translation, and that a parodist and a translator share a lot of features. Translation is assumed to be an attempt to approximate the original as close as possible, and in this attempt, one can identify a scale of varying distance between the original and the translations. These versions range from the most exact rendering of vocabulary and idiom to free translations to remarking of the original. It may also include radical translations, where no original is transferred to.

5. The Hermeneutic Motion Model of Translation:

Steiner (1976: 41) states that the translation is an every act of human speech. Humans, as users of language, attempt to translate each other's idiom. All communication is nothing but translation. The musical setting of words, the artist's illustration of a story, gestures and dances, are all modes of translation. The attempt to retrieve the speaker's information is, indeed, a process of translation. Interlingual translation, to which the term translation is often referred, is only the most salient, structurally defined case. In spite of that the hermeneutic motion of translations consists of four-fold steps. The first one is the trust, the belief, that the text we are confronted with has meaning that it has first of all sense, and then the sense which can be translated. This trust, thus, depends upon the sense, which should be elicited and translated. After trust comes aggressions, the translator extracts the sense from the text. The third one is the step which enables the translator to incorporate the extracted sense of the text. The fourth step is the piston-stroke which leads to the maintenance of parity between the original and the translated text. This is the step of compensation or restitution. This compensation or the maintenance of parity is absolutely essential to overcome the translator's interpretative attack and appropriation. Steiner further suggests that the paradigm of translations stays incomplete until the original has regained as much as it has lost. Steiner's view of translations is a hermeneutic motion that allows one to reject the triadic model which proposes only a distinction between literalism, paraphrase and free imitation. Thus, any translating material whether it is scientific or literary requires an expert handling of it.

6. Assessment of Translation:

Quality assessment is a vital process in any field of study and action, and more specifically in the field of translation where no practical methods of assessment are easily manageable and subjective or biased judgments can be seen widely. Nevertheless, the different scholars from different schools of thought view the concept of translation evaluation from different perspectives. House (2001) in her summarization included mentalists who had some subjective and intuitive evaluations. They believed that texts have no one meaning and their meanings change depending on the position of each of the individual speakers. Elsewhere she included behaviouristic scholars who aimed at a more scientific way of evaluating translations as belonging to what they call it a black box. Nida (1964) who was a supporter of this school of thought took the reader's reactions of translation as the main yardstick for assessing a quality of translation.

Functionalists such as Reiss and Vermeer (1984) claimed that purpose of a translation is the main item for qualifying a translation. The way target culture norms are treated or manipulated by a translation is the

crucial yardstick in evaluating a translation (House, 2001). Therefore, In text and discourse leaved approaches, translation was evaluated mainly in terms of its forms and functions in the target (receiving) culture and literature Toury, (1995). The source was subordinate to the target and what mattered was that translation is accepted as a tangible original work (and not a translation) in the target culture.

7. Translation Quality Assessment:

Evaluation is a need for any performances and the products or the results of any job in order to assess the quality of the final output. Michael Scriven (2007) a leading evaluation researcher, opines that the process of determining merit, worth, or significance: an evaluation is a product of that process. Professional evaluation is evaluation done in a systematic and objective way with a degree of expertise that requires extensive specific training or learning. The logic of evaluation is concerned with (i) how, if at all, professional evaluation is possible (ii) its nature and its location in the organization of knowledge and (iii) the logical structure of its significance.

Consequently, it is needed to define sets of values, worth or significances to be the basis of the evaluation and judgement in the field of translation.

Translation quality was long time assessed based on its being grammatically correct without taking into consideration the source text or units larger than sentence and also the context. The focus of this grammatical approach was the linguistic aspects of translation. During this time, translation studies were clearly defined as a sub-discipline of applied linguistics and it was the concept of equivalence became a key concept of translation studies Cyrus (2009). However, as Catford (1965) pointed out the central problems of translation practice is that of finding TL equivalents. A central task of translation theory is that of defining the nature and conditions of translations equivalence, while it was not easily possible to have a generally accepted definition or sets of criteria for this concept.

8. Equivalence and TQA:

View towards, this concept started from some linguistic approaches such as those belong to Savong (1957) in 'The Art of translation', who talk about equivalences rather contradictory way then the translation should render the words of the original and the ideas of the original as well. This way the translator shall seek a complete rebuild of the source into the target language, keeping the same linguistic form and semantic content. Following this definition, the slightest of deviations from the source would result in a defective translation, which can happen in almost all cases.

This goes on to some more target-oriented scholars such as Toury (1980) according to whom translation was designed to primarily fill a need in the target culture. Therefore it is logical to assume the target system as the object of the study. Thus, his approach towards equivalence was a target and product oriented one. He named equivalence as functional relational following the assumption that translation is the replacement of one message, which is enclosed in one natural language, by an equivalent message, encoded in another language.

Therefore, Translation is an act of communication, and equivalence in its best and most ideal mode can be the manifestation of the communication between the two culturally distinct groups of senders and receivers. This communication will take place if the intended meaning, or in this case, thoughts and intentions of author reflected in the translator's final job. In order to find out if such reflections actually happen, the researcher shall step away from the purely linguistic approaches.

9. Functional Equivalence:

The functions of a text are the application or use which the text has in the particular context of situation. We have to stress the fact that any text is embedded in a unique situation. In order to characterize the function of a text precisely analyse the text in detail. The purpose of establishing functional equivalence between source and a translation text (source text) to be analysed first and also to develop a model for the determination of the source text's function and the ensuing comparison of the source text and the translation's function this type of the notion of situation specifically called situational dimension. Crystal and Davy (1969) describe the original model of the situational dimension incorporating it into a tool for translation quality assessment.

A Dimension of Language User

Individuality

Dialect

Time

B Dimension of Language Use

a. (Simple / complex) Medium (speech, writing)

b. (Simple / complex) Participation (Monologue, Dialogue)

C Social Role Relationship

Province

Status

Modality

Singularity

While the purposes of constructing a model for situational functional source text analysis and translation match, in following manner:

- A. Dimensions of Language User:
 - 1. Geographical origin / Individuality
 - 2. Social class / Dialect
 - 3. Time
- B. Dimensions of Language Use
 - 1. Medium: simple / complex
 - 2. Participation: simple / complex
 - 3. Social Role Relationship:
 - 4. Social Attitude:
 - 5. Province:

10. Application of House's Model of Translation Quality Assessment:

Nida and Taber (1982) suggested some practiced tests for assessing translation quality. However, all those tests are characterized by an attempt to link translation quality to the effect of translation elicits in its reader. Thus they are based on the unwarranted assumption that greater ease of comprehension equals better translation. Some authors such as Wilss and Reiss, have made a potentially useful suggestion for translation assessment: the analysis of the source text prior to any evaluation of the translation text. However, these authors do not present any concrete suggestions on how to analyse the source text, the translation text, compare both and finally decide on the quality of the later. This is exactly what House (1981) attempts to do when proposing her model for translation quality assessment. Before presenting her model, House explains the theoretical basis on which her model was developed. She starts by saying that it is the essence of translation that meaning be preserved across the two languages involved, and that meaning has three basic aspects: a semantic, pragmatic and textual aspect.

The semantic aspect is the most easily accessible from the three aspects and has been given preference by evaluators. However, the pragmatic aspects, that is the particular use of an expression on a specific occasion. House's (1981: 27) approach is very important in translation because translation deals with Language in use.

The textual aspect has been frequently neglected though it is a very important aspect because all the references such as substitutions anaphora, ellipses etc., that make up the different ways of text constitution account for the textual meaning that should be preserved in translation.

Thus, according to House (1981: 29-30) translations would be the replacement of a text in the source language by a semantically and pragmatically equivalent text in the target language. The problem is then to explain what equivalence means. The equivalence sought should be an equivalence of function, that is both source and translation texts must present the same function and the function of the text can only be made explicit through a detailed analysis of the text itself. This is the basis for the model, and what makes it different from the order criteria for establishing equivalence because those criteria relied either on the writer's intention, an item that is not open to empirical investigation, or on the reader's responses, which presents problems to be measured.

The function of the text would then be 'the application (cf. Lyons 1969, 433) or use which the text has in the particular context of a situation. House (1981: 37) opines that each text is an individual text embedded in a unique situation, and to characterize the function of the text, it is necessary to refer to the text as per situation. To accomplish this, the notion of situation has to be broken down into the following specific situational dimensions.

A. Dimensions of Language User:

- **Geographical Origin:** features indicating the text's producer. Geographical origin – Tamil Nadu – marked form, standard Tamil literacy works in Tamil rendered into English.
- **Social Class:** features indicating the text's producer position on social scale – marked / unmarked form: Educated middle, high, class speaker's are known the standard language format in Tamil.
- **Time:** features indicating the text's temporal origin 3rd century.

B. Dimensions of Language use

- **Medium** - simple, The text is written / spoken to be heard and read; written to be made complex: The text is written to be highly literal form.
- **Participation** - Simple, monologue / conversation complex: The text contains features that show addresses participation.

C. Social Role Relationship:

- **Symmetrical:** The text contains features indicating solidarity and equality between addresser and addressees / encoding to decoding / writer to reader / speaker to listener.
- **Asymmetrical:** The text contains feature indicating authority relationship between addresser and addressees.

D. Social Attitude: The text contains feature indicating the degrees of social distance or proximity – five styles of formality, frozen, formal, consultative, causal and intimate.

E. Province: Field or topic of the text: details of text production.

The analysis of these situational dimensions leads to establishing the functions of a text. According to House ‘a translation text should not only match its source text in function, but employ equivalent situational – dimensional means to achieve that function’. House (1981: 49) observed that the match has to be verified along all the situational dimensions.

When analyzing the situational dimensions, House makes use of the following means for characterizing the linguistic evidence present in the text: syntactic means; lexical means and textual means. The textual means comprise theme dynamics, classical linkage and iconic linkage.

In addition to using the situational dimensions just mentioned, House utilized the following device when analyzing and comparing source and translation texts: Symbols such as(+human),(-human),(+ abstract), (- abstract): rhetorical – stylistic concepts such as alliteration and anacoluthon; other concepts, such as foregrounding x automatization, illocutionary force, emic vs etic texts, ideational and interpersonal functions, textual features, such as overall logical structure and the presence of redundancy.

House also relies on her native speaker’s intuition and on the judgements of other native speakers, which are taken as hypothesis. House believes that equivalence relations between two languages are not absolute but they fall on a scale of more or less equivalent items which runs from more or less probable. This degree of probability can only be judged by a subjective, hermeneutic element as the native speaker intuition.

As a result of analysis just mentioned, a textual profile is established for the source text under the form of a statement of function. The translation text is then analysed using the same dimensions, and its textual profile is determined. The comparison of the two textual profile reveals the degree to which the translation text matches the source text being therefore adequate in quality, and a statement of quality is provided.

11. Errors:

Translation quality assessment, in order to overcome the inadequacies, attempts to assess translation quality. It is the norm of usage which being a part of the competence of reader’s centered metalingual judgements. However, it has to bear in mind it depend on the individual choice of translator as well as readers. Koller (1974) and Reiss (1968) approach to the problems of translation quality assessment which leads to good or highly intelligible etc., but according to ‘adequate’ or inadequate as far as given text concerned.

If a Target Language text, in order to be adequate, it has to fulfil the requirement of a dimensional and as a result of these functional matches. Any mismatches along with the situational dimensions are constitutes of an errors. Such a dimensional errors, in terms of covertly erroneous errors, must be clearly differentiated from those of overtly erroneous errors, which results either from mismatches of the denotative meanings of Source Language Text and Target Language Text elements or from a breach of the target language system. Corder (1973).

12. Covertly Erroneous Errors:

A covert translation is called for whenever a Source Language Text is not source – culture linked, and does not have independent status in the Source Language community: a covert translation is not marked pragmatically as a TT of an ST but it will equally have been created as its own right. The translation is covert because it is not marked pragmatically as a TT of an ST, but may, conceivably, have been created in its own right. A covert translation is thus a translation whose ST is not specifically addressed to a target culture audience (i.e. not particularly tied to the Source Language Community and Culture. An ST and its covert TT are pragmatically of equal concern for the Source and Target Language addressees. Both are, as it were, equally directly addressed. An ST and its covert TT have equivalent purposes: they are based on contemporary, equivalent needs of a comparable audience in the Source and Target Language Communities. In the case of covert TTs, it is thus both possible and desirable to keep the function of ST equivalent in TT. For example,

Cultural Items:

- | | | | |
|----|---|-------------------|-------------------|
| 1. | aNikalan (nakai, alaku) | (Ch. 58, K - 575) | |
| | kaNNiRku aNikalam kaNNooTTam | | - SL |
| | Benignity is eye’s adorning grace | | - TL ₁ |
| | . . . ornaments of the eyes | | - TL ₂ |
| | . . . kind looks are jewels for eyes to wear . . . | | - TL ₃ |
| 2. | ami ^l tu | (Ch. 7: K - 64) | |
| | ami ^l tinum aRRa in ^{itee} tam makkaL | | - SL |
| | Than God’s ambrosia sweeter far the food . . . | | - TL ₁ |
| | . . . far sweeter (to the parent) than ambrosia | | - TL ₂ |
| | The food is more than nectar sweet. . . | | - TL ₃ |
| | a ⁿ kaNattuL ukka ami ^l taRRaal | (Ch. 72: K - 720) | - SL |
| | Ambrosia in the sewer spilt, is word | | - TL ₁ |
| | . . . dropping nectar on the ground | | - TL ₂ |

	Pours ambrosia into gutters		-	TL ₃
	peetaikku amiltin iyanRana tool	(Ch. 111: K - 1106)	-	SL
	Ambrosia are the simple maiden's arms		-	TL ₁
	The shoulders of this fair one are made of ambrosia . . .		-	TL ₂
	My simple maid has nectar arms		-	TL ₃
	In Source Language text form 'amiltu' instead of 'Ambrosia' has been found in three places in translated text in English ThirukkuRaL as far the same in SL text.			
3.	avi (ney)	(Ch. 26: K - 259)		
	avi corintu aayiram veeTTalin		-	SL
	Than thousand rich oblations, with libations rare,			
	Better the flesh of slaughtered beings not to share		-	TL ₁
	. . . Better than the pouring forth of ghee etc., in			
	thousands sacrifices		-	TL ₂
	. . . truly excels thousand pourings of ghee!		-	TL ₃
4.	annai (taai)	(Ch. 115: K - 1147)		
	annai col niiraaka niiLum innooy. . .		-	SL
	. . . my mother's word doth water it.		-	TL ₁
	. . . watered by the (harsh) words of my mother.		-	TL ₂
	. . . mother's refrain. . .		-	TL ₃
5.	anicchappuu (anicchamalar)	(Ch. 112: K - 1115)		
	anicchappuuk kaal kaLaiyaan peytaan		-	SL
	The flowers of the sensitive plant as a griddle around. . .		-	TL ₁
	. . . anicham without having removed		-	TL ₂
	Anicha flower with stem . . .		-	TL ₃
6.	Aniccham (naaka mallikai)	(Ch. 9: K - 90)		
	mooppak kulaiyum aniccham		-	SL
	The flower of 'Anicha' withers away.. if you.. inhale		-	TL ₁
	As Anciam flower fades in smelling		-	TL ₂
	Anicham smelt wither's; . . .		-	TL ₃
	nanniirai vaaLi anicchamee	(Ch. 112: K - 1111)	-	SL
	O flower of the sensitive plant! than thee. . .		-	TL ₁
	May you flourish, O Anicham! . . .		-	TL ₂
	Soft blessed anicha flower, . . .		-	TL ₃
	anicchamum annattin tuuvium maataraTikku	(Ch. 112: K - 1120)		
	The flower of the sensitive plant, and . . .			
	swam's white breast		-	TL ₁
	The anicham and the feathers of the swan		-	TL ₂
	The soft flower and the swan's down. . .		-	TL ₃
7.	aaNi (kaTai aaNi)	(Ch. 67: K - 667)		
	acchaaNi annaarutaittu. . .			
	. . . like Linch-pin of the mighty car!		-	TL ₁
	. . . the world has those who resemble the linch-pin			
	of the big rolling care		-	TL ₂
	Like linch-pin of big rolling car		-	TL ₃
	uluvaar ulakattaarkku aaNi. . .	(Ch. 104: K -1032)		
	The ploughers are the linch-in of the world. . .		-	TL ₁
	Agriculturists are the linch-pin of the world . . .		-	TL ₂
	Tillers are linch-pin of mankind bearing the rest		-	TL ₃

The cultural item of the words most probably untranslated in all the three Target Language texts. All the three translators retain the same Source Language words as far as original concerned.

13. Overtly Erroneous Errors:

In the process of evaluating, the non-dimensional mismatches or overtly erroneous errors, the latter type of error comprising both mismatches of denotation meanings of ST and TT elements and breaches of the target language system. However, the sub-group of overtly erroneous errors referred to the mismatches of the denotative meaning of ST and TT elements. It will detract more seriously from the quality of a TT than dimensional mismatches, whenever the ST has a strongly marked ideational functional component. A detailed hierarchy of errors will depend in any given case, on the particular objective(s) of the evaluation. The Translation quality assessment in which the translator could suggested in order to distinctions between a covert and an overt translation, a translation and version, and its resultant consequences for the practice of translation and the assessment of translations quality. The proposed model may be used for assessing an overt versions'

adequacy given a precise specification of the way. The overt version's function differs from ST's function; the functional change may be 'added' to ST's textual profile, and the amended profile is to be taken on the norm against which overt version can be measured.

- | | | | |
|-----|---|--------------------|---|
| 1. | CiRukai aLaaviya kuul
... the food ... in which the little hands ... play'd ...
The rice in which the little hand ... has dabbled
The food. . . in which one's children hands insert | (Ch. 7 : K – 64) | - SL
- TL ₁
- TL ₂
- TL ₃ |
| 2. | paTaikuTikuul amaiccu naTpu araN aaRu. . .
An army, people, wealth, a minister, friends, fort . . .
. . . an army, a people, wealth, minister, friends and fortress, . . .
people, troops, wealth, forts, council, friends, . . . | (Ch. 39 : K – 381) | - SL
- TL ₁
- TL ₂
- TL ₃ |
| 3. | painkuul kaLai kaTTatanoTu neer
as . . . farmer frees from weeds the tender grain
like pulling up the weeds in the green corn.
. . . behold, weeds removes from cropful field | (Ch. 55 : K – 550) | - SL
- TL ₁
- TL ₂
- TL ₃ |
| 4. | kuulum kuTiyum oruŋkilakkum kool kooTi
. . . his wealth and people utterly shall lose
Will lose at once both his wealth and his subjects
The king shall wealth and subjects lose . . . | (Ch. 56: K - 554) | - SL
- TL ₁
- TL ₂
- TL ₃ |
| 5. | koNTa kuujittaaki akattaar nilaikkeLitaam
Impregnable, containing ample stores of food . . .
Which abounds in suitable provisions ..
Impregnable, with stores of food cosy to live... | (Ch. 74: K - 745) | - SL
- TL ₁
- TL ₂
- TL ₃ |
| 9. | Caavaa maruntu (amiItam, teevaruNavu)
caavaa marunteninum veenTaRpaaRRaRu
Though food of immortality . . . is thing abhorred
. . . Though <i>he were eating</i> the food of immortality.
Albeit you eat nectar - like food. | (Ch. 9: K - 82) | - SL
- TL ₁
- TL ₂
- TL ₃ |
| 10. | tukil (aaTai)
maatar paTaa mulaimel tukil
The silken cincture's folds invest
This maiden's panting breast
The cloth that covers the firm bosom of this maiden . . .
Vest on the buxom breast of her . . . | (Ch.109: K -1087) | - SL
- TL ₁
- TL ₂
- TL ₃ |
| 11. | puusanai (valipaaTu)
ciRappoTu puusanai cellaatu vaanam vaRakkumeel . . .
If heaven grow dry, with feast and offering never more
If heaven dry up, neither yearly festivals nor daily worship . . .
will be offered
beneath a barren sky, would offerings for the gods deny. | (Ch.2: K -18) | - TL ₁
- TL ₂
- TL ₃ |
| 12. | puRam (veLiyiTam, veLippakkam)
puRaŋkunRi kaNTanaiya reenum. . .
Outward, they shine as 'kunRi' berry's scarlet bright
. . . persons whose outside appears as the berry of the
the abrus
. . . Berry red is his outward view . . . | (Ch.28: K - 277) | - SL
- SL
- TL ₁
- TL ₂
- TL ₃ |

The ideational function of text in TL Thirukku RaL in English by G.U. Pope Rev. Drew and Kaviyogi Sudhanantha Bharathi covertly and overtly translated the source language text rendered into target language 'sense-to-sense' translation. But, Rev. Drew rendered into his target language, there are 9th example used as ungrammatical sentence 'he were eating' the food of immortality. The correct form is 'they were eating' the food of immortality in TL₂ text, and overtly transferred the message in 10th example 'tukil' (aaTai) the SL text 'maatar paTaa mulaimel tukil' refers to 'buxom of this maiden's panting breast'. The denotative meaning and metaphorical construction of the structure of the sentence is found in TL text. Therefore, the translators think about the original sense which may convey to the Target Language readers without affecting the fact of the messages.

14. Comparison of SL Text into TL Text:

Method - A

Method – A describes in full experiment, setting up of the test, among other things of languages. It is based on error analysis and required the evaluator to identify possible errors in method – A. In appropriate renderings which affect the understanding of the source language text; these are divided into five categories:

additions, omissions, unresolved extralinguistic references, loss of meaning and inappropriate linguistic variation (i.e. register, style, dialect etc.) In appropriate renderings which affect expression in the target language; there are, spelling, grammar, lexical items, and style. Inadequate renderings are found which transmit the information and either the main function or secondary function of the source text affected.

Method – B

Method – B is also based on error analysis, but requires the evaluator to calculate the effect of the errors detected.

Method – C

Method - C is a holistic method and it requires the evaluator to assess the translation to a series of descriptors in different levels of achievement. Method - C is a holistic method which leads to correction of the following features: One is, it presents a unitary scale which considers the translation competence as a whole, instead of dividing it into various sub-scales representing different sub-competences. Secondly, the descriptors do not use terminology that World presuppose specialist knowledge (such as applied linguistics) on the part of the correctors. Thirdly, it includes only five levels in an attempt to achieve maximum consistency between the Target Language text and Source Language text.

Applying these methods, in different order (A/B/C, C/B/A/, B/A/C etc.,) to control the variable of one method influencing the following one. In case of method A and B the individual potential of the same knowledge acquired, method B, explains the difference between language mistakes and translation mistakes. Perhaps, the most important criterion was that of marking everything in the translation which was clearly acceptable in G.U. Pope’s ThirukkuRaL Translation: Some of the correctors, in view of the fact that the translation of ThirukkuRaL by Pope, translating into foreign language, initially tempted to be free translation, especially when it came to judging, to translation difficult versions which would have obviously inter-reliability. On his translation corrected by the evaluator had awarded as a ‘good’ or satisfactory.

Table 1: Holistic Assessment in English Translations of ThirukkuRaL

Level	Accuracy of transfer of Source Language text into TL text	Quality of expressions in Target Language Text	Degree of task completion	Remarks
1	Totally adequate transfer of SLT content; the translator is becoming worth.	The translator reveals a total lack of ability to express himself adequately in target language text	Totally adequate in all three text	Good
2	Transfer undermined by serious inaccuracies; through the professional standard	Almost the entire text reads like a translation there are continual lexical, grammatical or spelling errors are not found	Totally adequate in all three text	Good
3	Transfer of the general idea(s) but with a number of lapses are not found; needs considerable professional standards are maintained	Certain parts read like a piece originally written in English, verse form but others read like prose forms. There are a considerable number of lexical, grammatical or spelling errors are found in prose forms. In poetic version only one place found in spelling error in particular text	Adequate in all three text	Good
4	Almost complete transfer; professional standard	Originally written in English especially old English, middle English, and old French and Latin Greek, Archaic forms are used. Lexical, grammatical or spelling, errors are not found in entire text.	Almost completely successful in all three text	Better
5	Complete transfer of Source Language Text: translation equivalence found in professional standard	Almost the entire text written English especially old English, middle English and old French & Latin Greek, Archaic forms are used.	Successful in all three text	Best

Table 2: Stands on Errors found in English Translations of ThirukkuRaL

Riccardo Schiaffino and Franco Zero (2005) states that the language quality is measured such as design, calibration, sampling, measurement, analysis and processes of improvement. The Translations of the Language quality especially the following manner of the errors found in general.

S.No	Type of Errors	SL	TL1	TL2	TL3	Remarks
1.	Errors of meaning	Not applicable	Meaning errors not found	Meaning errors not found	Meaning errors not found	Nil
2.	Errors of form	Not applicable	Accuracy in grammar, not found in grammatical errors. spelling errors found in 99 th kuRaL, chapter10. For instance ‘repellent’ instead of ‘repellent’ in TL ₁ .	Found in spelling error, grammatical error not found	Spelling errors are found grammatical errors not found	Nil
3.	Errors of compliance	Not applicable	(+ archaic forms) are used +Old English + Middle English + Latin + French words are used. +American English words	Traditional forms are used	Traditional forms are used	+archaic forms + Latin, French words are in TL texts

The above mentioned errors are common to all language. While translating the Source Language into Target Language text, the language part has those aspects of error which commit all the three translations namely G.U. Pope, Drew and Kaviyogi Sudhanantha Bharathi. But, all the erroristic view of the translators are overlooked to handle all the problems in the process of ‘ThirukkuRaL’ translations. The language and stylistic problem is the biggest problem then the terminology and formatting of the language in a particular Target language than the performing of the accuracy in the manner of readability in the sense of the readers response and what have to translate and to whom we are concerned to translate.

The functions of language have been influenced in order to gain some clarity about the concept of referential and non-referential meaning of the word as well as context. Ogden and Richards (1946) pointed out five functions namely symbolization of references, expression of attitude to listener, expression of attitude to referent promotion of effects intended and support of reference emotive-expressive and the conative-persuasive textual types. Similarly Omen (1971) differentiates two basic textual functions and two textual types on the basis of use of language. According to Lyons (1969) the functions of language of the texts is application or use which the text has in the particular context of situation.

15. Analysis of TLT and Statement of the Function:

Dimension of Language User

- Geographical origin : marked, standard medical English
- Social class : marked educated middle, high class
- Time : marked contemporary medieval English.

Dimension of Language Use

Medium Simple, written to be read, as realized by the linguistic means.

Syntactic Means: a) Absence of elliptical clause, phrase, words and contractions of sentences, contact parentheses and comment parentheses and any kind of poetic personal pronouns, you, your, they, thyself, and thou, thee and their, are used in the possessive case and objective case which will be used in the entire text.

For Example:

All the personal pronouns are analyzed in SL text and in TL₁, and TL₃ texts, which most probably used in poetical versions used as possessive and objective case.

Table 4: Analysis of Personal Pronouns in TL Texts

Person	Singular			Plural		
	Nominative Case	Possessive Case	Objective Case	Nominative Case	Possessive Case	Objective Case
First person	I	My Mine (arah)	Me	We	Our Ours	Us
Second Person	Thou (arah) you	Thy Thine (arah) You Yours	Thee (arah) You	Ye You	Yours truly, Yours Yours truly, Yours	You You
Third person Masculine	He	His	Him	They	Their Theirs Their Theirs	Them
Feminine	She	Her Hers	Her	They	Their	Them
Neuter	It	Its	It	They	Theirs	Them

b) Subject and object positions are alternatively used in Translated version

For Example,

- iRaivanaTi ceerntaar piRaviperuñkadal niintuvaar (Ch. 1: K – 10)
- iRaivanati ceeraataar piRavi peruñkaTal niintaar - SL
- rendering in English,
- The monarch’s foot who gain they swim’ the sea of births - TL₁
- (Sentence 1)
- The monarch’s foot none others reach the shore of being mighty main
- (Sentence-2)

Presence of Subject Deletion Rule is Found

- For Example iraivan aTi (1)
- iraivan aTi (2)

‘iraivanaTi₋₁’ and ‘iravanaTi₋₂’ is also identical noun phrase in the deep structure of the sentence. Syntactically, two identical noun is deleted in the same construction. The subject of the noun phrase (NP) is deleted in TL text.

Modification:

Most of the places in TLT ‘KuRaL’ expanded the modifications found in the same structure of SL Text in the sense of change in word order.

For Example,

- | | | | |
|----|---|---|-----------------|
| 2. | malarmicai eekinaaṅ maaNaTi ceernthaaṅ
nilamicai niiTuvaal vaar.
rendering into TL text | - | SL |
| | (Ch. 1 : K – 3) | | |
| | In bliss long time shall dwell above the earthly pain | - | TL ₁ |
| | instead of, | | |
| | niiTu + vaal + vaar | | |
| | longtime + (in bliss) shall dwell (who) | | |

Lexical means

- a) presence of the adjectives, metaphors, alliteration, assonance, onomatopoeia, puns and word plays are found.
- b) frequently used adjectives and adverbs which formulated the adverbial phrase and adjectival phrase in target language text are found.
- c) use of [+archaic] lexical items, French, old French, English ME, OE words and also Latin words are found.

Textual means: The text has a well-organized, logical structure, use of definite poetical cataphoric pronouns are used, e.g. thy, thin, thee, those etc, the text is emic i.e., determined exclusively through text-immanent criteria.

Participation: Simple, monologue as well as dialogue with anticipated, directed addressee reactions.

Social role relationship:

A symmetrical role relationship: addresser assumes moral authority over the addressees.

Position role of addresser: teacher, philosopher *situational role of the addresser:* writer of didactic i.e., instructional, educational, education, informative, informational, edifying, improving, perceptive, pedagogic, moralistic etc.

The addresser tries to improve the moral behaviour of the addressees by providing them with the moral behaviour of other people.

Social Attitude

Consultative, a conversational style, is found designed to match the way the addressers would normally speak in everyday conversations.

Syntactic means: Presence of direct, indirect speech, active Vs passive sentences and complex compound sentences are found.

Lexical means: Use of lexical [+archaic, +traditional) forms frequently used are adjectives and adverbs. Overall organizing the lexical forms which explicit moralizing instructions as to how the addressees ought to react to the ensuing two-anecdotes. The addresser puts a rhetorical questions to the addressees. Thus, guiding their moral instructions. In the second part, the addressees are being questioned as to the nature of lesson to be learned from the anecdotes and a direction is given as to their future moral behaviour.

Textual means: The text denotes independent of the enveloping situation of production and directs the addressee to react. The analysis is supported by the fact that the addresser presents the anecdotes as illustrations of generally valid truth, a common trait in moral values of human life.

Province: Target text shows in value of education, character, hospitality, family responsibilities, social service, public awareness, civic rights and duties, responsibilities of government, communication principles, management techniques, engineering, science and technology, sanctity of love, purpose of life, etc. in universal outlook. The kuRaL (994) illustrates the human role of life. The following linguistic means:

Graphical means: Presence of capital words referring to deity, as an individuality or humanity as whole. It refers to kuRaL, ‘A’ is the first letter of all letters, every speech maintains. Instead, the ‘Primal Deity’ is referred to as ‘supreme of the God of all living being’. In whole of text the capitalization is also frequently used to emphasize particular lexical items. Use of italics and double quotations are emphasize certain words and phrases.

For example,

1. “Primal deity” (Ch.1: K - 1)
2. “Let it rain” (Ch. 6: K - 55)
3. “I shall perish” (Ch. 12: K - 6)
4. “He is without virtue” (Ch. 20: K - 193)
5. “I have nothing” (Ch. 23: K - 205)

The double quotative part was used by G.U. Pope in one place, Drew used in thirty two places and Sudhanantha Bharathi used in twenty eight places out of one thousand three hundreden thirty kuRaLs.

Syntactic means:

a) Excessively, use of the present tense, past tense, past participle, future tense to express the eternal truth’ of what is being stated in throughout the text is found where ever it needs.

b) Frequently the copula form or coordinate connective noun phrase is used in the entire text. This is typical of the multitude of existential, descriptively identified the statement of philosophical nature.

c) Presence of alteration between the sentence levels, it follows as declaration, interrogation, imperative and exclamatory sentences. This achieves a dramatic and emotive effect from the whole text in TLT.

Lexical means:

Use of specifically traditional [+ archaic words] and Latin, OE, ME French words which leads to form the phrases is found throughout the text.

Presence of figurative language and metaphorical language are frequently used along with intensifier and superlatives in the entire text wherever it needs.

For example

- | | | | |
|----|---|-------------------|---|
| 1. | aruLennum <i>anpiin kulavi</i> poruLennum
celvac ceviliyaal uNTu.
'Tis love that <i>kindliness as off spring bears</i> ;
And wealth as bounteous nurse the infant rears.
The <i>child mercy</i> which is borne by love grows
Under the care of the rich nurse of wealth.
Grace, the child of love, is nourished
By the <i>wet-nurse</i> of wealth cherished. | (Ch. 16. K – 757) | - SL
- TL ₁
- TL ₂
- TL ₃ |
|----|---|-------------------|---|

In Source Language text 'anpiin kulavi' has been rendered into TL₁, TL₂ and TL₃, 'Kindliness as offspring bears', 'Child mercy' and 'wet-nurse' respectively. KSB translates 'anpiin kulavi' in SL into 'wet-nurse' in TL text treating as metaphorical property of the language, but not used in TL₁ and TL₂.

In ThirukkuRaL, Metaphorical constructions used in SL, are rendered into TL while transferring the message.

Metaphor arising problem in translation on the basis of comparison between source language into target language which has been literary technique from ancient times. Aristotle (1978), the Greek critic and theoretician, deals with metaphors in his treatises on poetic and Rhetoric's and with simile in Rhetoric's. He pays special attention to metaphor; and treats simile only as an extension of it. Longiners (1978) who recognizes the importance of figures of speech in literature when he denotes them a place in his sources of sublimit. Modern scholars and literary critics acknowledge the place of these figures of speech in the literary form in various ways. Some consider them as part of imagery. Ullmann (1964) regards them as deviant usages of language According to Leech (1989) and Aristotle (1978) Metaphor is one of the divisions of noun. Hence, the inclusion of metaphor in the poetic structure is achieved at the language stratum.

In ThirukkuRaL translation, there are six kuRaLs has the metaphorical poetic structures, out of one thousand three hundreden thirty kuRaLs. (K – 757, 936, 1168, 1147, 1164 and 1261).

Textual means

When the Presence of the particularization and generalization of the 'theme' is in which extended to explaining, interpreting and modifying a strong textual cohesion. The textual cohesion in the case of this particular text, of emphasis, includes the following:

- a) Repetition of lexical items which occur in the except from the social usages. It acts as 'keywords' with vastly different collocation potential and rich connotations.
- b) Frequent use of partial synonymy, polysemy, opposition forms, emotive forms in particular context and in particular clausal elements.

Statement of function

The addresser's main purpose is to inform the people of the following as precisely as possible: rights in morality of the life of the virtue which is not interrupted by the addressees participation.

All dimensions clearly operate in support of the ideational functional component through the use of well-structured sentences, structures that give the text a formal tone, precise moral instruction which made strong textual cohesion and explicit consideration of acceptable alternative interpretations in Drew and KSB renderings. The text indicates that there is no attempt to make them attractive to the addressees in KSB works. Therefore, the writer's intention seems to be to render important information efficiently.

The interpersonal component is marked only to minor degree by the use of the illocutionary force of order in the utterance showing the asymmetrical relationship existing between the addresser and the moral ethics. And also the consistent use of the modal verb *shall*, seems to emphasize to the addressees that those are texts that express obligations that must be fulfilled by the both of the translators. The interpersonal component is also supported by the use of the imperative form in one of the contracts.

Analysis of Translation Texts: The analysis of the translation texts revealed the following mismatches.

Covertly Erroneous Errors

Medium : Symmetry

Syntactic means : reduction of long appositional phrases, omission of items in the rendering of Drew and Sudhanantha Bharathi.

Oppositional Phrases

1. kaalai arumpiyap pakalellaam (Ch. 123 : K – 1227)

maalai malarum

Kalai arumpi

X

Maalai malarum

my grief at morn a bud,

X

full-blown expands in evening hour

- TL₁

This malady buds forth in the morning

X

. . . blossoms in the evening

- TL₂

Budding pangs . . .

This disease blooms in evening gay

- TL₃

The above oppositional forms 'kaalai X maalai' rendering in TL₁ and TL₂ 'morn x evening' in the some of the contextual usages. But in TL₃ Sudhanantha Bharathi has used the term 'budding', a word which connote the meaning of the word in a contextual morning 'time of blossoms of any flower' that's like to say 'love is budding in the morning' sense 'maalai' malarum. This disease blooms in evening time in TL₃. Therefore in TL₁ and TL₂, the structure of the oppositional phrase are rendered in SL to TL text without affecting the original message in TL₃.

2. paNiyumaam enRum perumai ciRumai (Ch.98: K - 978)

aNiyumaam tannai viyantu.

- SL

paniyumaam perumai . . .

X

aniyumaam ciRumai . . .

Greatness humbly bends . . . but

X

Littleness always spreads out . . .

- TL₁

The great will always humble

- TL₂

Greatness bends with modesty

Meanness vaunts with vanity

- TL₃

The opposition phrase in kuRaL (978) 'perumai x ciRumai', has been rendered into 'greatness x littleness' in TL₁ and 'great will always humble; but the mean will. . . self-admiration' in TL₂. The presupposing the meaning of the context leads to the self-admired in humbleness in the nature the truth. But in TL₃ the rendering 'Greatness bends with modesty, meanness vaunts with vanity', does not lead to proper opposition in the form of the context. Yet, the meaning is understood for the kuRaL readers.

3. toonRiR pukaḷooTu toonRuka . . . (Ch. 24: K - 236)

toonRalin toonRaamai nanRu

- SL

. . . appear adorned with glory's grace;

. . . 't were better hide your face

- TL₁

. . . be born with qualities conducive to fame . . .

. . . not to be born

- TL₂

Be born with fame . . .

If not of birth you must not vaunt

- TL₃

In the above kuRaL (236) 'toonRuka x toonRaamai' means 'born x (or) not to be born' in the context of the meaning in TL₁, TL₂ and TL₃, that is the meaning which will constitute transparency of the birth in all the three translated text.

Lexical means

Abundant in [+archaic forms] derivatives from here and there: [+formal- formal] are inadequate translation in KSB and Drew's renderings in 'kuRaL'.

Textual means

Omissions of temporal deities forthwith, then and immediately; omissions were found in KSB and Drew translations from SL to TL text in kuRaL.

Participations

Omissions of the phrase, clause, sentence, an illocutionary force of order, omission of the only phrase in one of the STs in which the addressers' participation is elicited- if address is incorrect.

Social role relationship

Use of [technical] forms, [+archaic forms] traditional words are implemented to explicit the noticing of the words. Translation should be the royalty and copyright, instead of maintaining the terms in Latin, French and Old English, Middle English, ME in G.U. Pope's rendering of SL into TL text.

Syntactic means

Corrected phrases, rendered in old and middle English with use of traditional forms.

Lexical means

Omission of [+formal] terms, use of [-formal] terms.

Province

Graphical means

Capitalization, mostly abundant use of double quotative bold face type than ST text.

Syntactic means

Past tense, future perfect tense with connotation inconsistent translations model of verb shall be translated in [o] in many places in TT text. This is for the strong element of textual cohesion in contracts in entire text.

Lexical means

Omission of several items causing the text to less precise or emphatic than the ST; lack of lexical retains presented in ST to TT in order to first line to second line of the couplets in KSB and Drew's renderings.

Textual means

- a) **Theme dynamics:** lack of anaphoric referencing, lack of repetition of lexical items that function as key words are expressing theme of the word sequences.
- b) **Clausal linkage:** omission of logical connector, then, and while even, eventhough, thus, etc.

Overtly Erroneous Errors

Breaches of the Target Language system

Cases of ungrammaticality

Wrong verbs are used.

For example,

Rev. Drew make as incorrect wrong verb used.

viruntu puRattataat taanuNTal caavaa marunte <u>n</u> inum veeNTaaRpaaR nan <u>Ru</u>	(Ch. 9: K - 82)	-	SL
Though food of immortality . . . feasting alone, the guest without unfed, is thing abhorred		-	TL ₁
. . . Eventhough <i>he were eating</i> the food of immortality		-	TL ₂
.			
Albeit you eat nectar- like food		-	TL ₃

In the above mentioned, 'though food of immortality' feasting alone', a noun clause in TL₁ and . . . 'he were eating the food of immortality' in TL₂ instead of 'he were eating the food' is an ungrammatical structure; and meaning of the context in TL₂ rendered by Rev. Drew is incorrect.

Kaviyoogi Sudhanantha Bharathi in TL₃ rendered into 'nectar – like food you eat'. TL₂ referred to third person singular masculine 'he' and 'you eat' in TL₂ second person singular/masculine (or) feminine in general and also TL₂ past – continuous, TL₃ past tense are found.

❖ Case of Dubious acceptability

Literal translation causing a lexical repetition that makes the sentence sound awkward.

Mismatches of Denotative Meaning

- ❖ **Omissions:** important references to other documents and to the contract itself are lost with the omission of *there under and hereunder*.
- ❖ **Insertion :** Insertion of the phrase meter and length establishing a condition that is not present in the TT text in Koviyoogi Sudhanantha Bharathi's version.

16. Conclusion:

Statement of Quality Assessment:

The omissions of several derivatives from here and there not only impair comprehension and thus weaken the ideational component of textual function, but also exclude from the TTs items. And also rhyme and rhythm, rhetorical functions, which are implied in Pope's rendering, are not found much more in Drew's and KSB's renderings of English 'kuRaL'. These features are excluded from the TTs items which are typically used in formal written text.

The ideational component is also compromised by the non-use of cohesive devices and precise of moral ethical works.

The interpersonal functional component is violated in many instances in Drew's and KSB's renderings. The degree of equality between the writer / author / translator of the contract and its readers is altered in TL texts (i.e. Pope's renderings like poetic verse, Drew's rendering prose verse, but KSB's rendering is only poetic versions).

The TL texts lose part of the intimating power of the impersonal language that the ST's provides. The non-utilization of the graphical means present in the ST's impairs the interpersonal component while lessening the potential and emotive functions are also impact of the text. Also, the emphatic effects displayed in the ST's

through theme – rhyme, rhythmic distribution which only offered by Pope’s translation; and structural parallelism not matched in the Drew’s and KSB’s renderings in TL Texts.

In addition, the translations of ‘shall’ weaken both components of the textual functions in Drew and Kaviyogi Suthanantha Barathi’s renderings in TL texts.

So far the problems of the present TL texts are related to overtly erroneous errors. These errors detract from a clear and efficient passing on the information. Thus, the ideational component which is strongly marked in this type of text is violated to a considerable extent in the Drew’s and KSB’s translations

The overtly erroneous errors found, also cause impact on the interpersonal functional component. This happens especially in one of the contracts by the deletions / omissions the only instance in which the addressees are invited to participate in the form of the assessment in overall translation of ThirukkuRal in English (target language text), are verified and clarified from the part of the functional approach which can be followed in the further research in future.

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